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दूरस्थ माध्यम से अध्यापक शिक्षा कार्यक्रमों में सूचना एवं संप्रेषण तकनीक की भूमिका का अध्ययन	डॉ. अश्वनी	54

ALLURING USE OF POWERPOINT IN LECTURES: MORE TECHNOLOGY, LESS LEARNING

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Abstract

PowerPoint (© Microsoft Corp.) is a widely used presentation programme that originated in the world of business but has now become commonplace in the world of educational technology. However, its use is far from controversial in this educational context and opinions as to its use range from highly supportive to significantly negative. One of the major problems is that its current use is frequently limited to an information transmission mode, often with excessive content and distracting animation effects. This paper reviews the advantages, disadvantages and precautions associated with its use in a teaching and learning context and suggest some guidelines and pedagogical strategies that need to be considered where it is to be used. It summarises some of the key principles of presentation that are frequently ignored and suggests some of the approaches that need to be incorporated into good practice.

Technology has become a major part of most classrooms, and curriculum in the past 10 years. "Learning sciences research tells us that students learn much better 'by doing' rather than 'by listening'. Thus, passive learning – the traditional lecture- is being replaced in our classrooms by more active learning activities that emphasize student problem solving, discussion, presentation, and other "authentic learning-by-doing activities" (Day & Groeneweg, 2004, p.1). With the advancements that are being made in software development and the availability of these programs to students, there are many opportunities to learn using non-traditional methods. PowerPoint is one such software program that is being used in the classroom as a tool to incorporate active learning activities into the curriculum. PowerPoint has the potential to be an effective tool for both teachers and students to engage in active learning activities. PowerPoint enables teachers and students to actively create presentations with graphics, charts, diagrams, and pictures in their slideshows to help make often complicated ideas and lessons more manageable and understandable. It is a way for students to actively engage in research, and present information to their peers.

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The ability to increase clarity, develop and sustain interest in the subject, show pictures/illustrations/animations as an explanatory device and to reinforce main points of lectures are some of the primary purposes of using visual aids like PowerPoint. Therefore PowerPoint should be used for only these purposes during a lecture (Sagar, 2011). The effectiveness of a particular medium depends not so much upon the medium, but on how it is used. The media do not influence student achievement any more than the 'truck that delivers our groceries' causes changes in our nutrition (Clarke, 1993). Thus, though technology has been recognized as having a great potential to enhance student achievement, this purpose is achieved only if it is used appropriately (Bransford *et al.*, 2000).

Presentation software has become an accepted lecture aid in higher education and is frequently used to visually present the main points of classroom lectures. At present, PowerPoint is the best-known and most popular presentation software. According to Yaworski (2001), PowerPoint helps speakers organize their thoughts and present them in a clear and concise manner while using multisensory tactics to hold audience attention. PowerPoint allows a lecturer to take advantage of the educational benefits of using visual aids and technology in lectures in order to improve the effectiveness of teaching and learning. Teaching with PowerPoint does not necessarily involve radical changes to teaching approaches, though it can if the lecturer so wishes. Even as a tool to create better designed black and white or colour transparencies, the default settings of the PowerPoint software require a lecturer to abide by, or at least consider, basic principles of instructional design in the point sizes of text, bullet points, framing and layout of slides (Jackson, 1997). The results of the student survey suggest that lecturers should take particular care in designing their PowerPoint presentations and to ensure that they are not so over-featured as to become distracting.

The PowerPoint presentation program is undoubtedly one of the most controversial pieces of technology to emerge in the last 25 years. Some like it and use it a great deal because of the many advantages like accessibility, ease of use, professional look, etc. Others dislike it and associate its use with the development of a reductionist lousy way of thinking like little depth, oversimplification of information, useless visual distractions, etc. According to Brown (2007), the problem is not with the software, but with its users. It is therefore possible to

improve the situation by helping PowerPoint users to develop better quality presentations.

The traditional lecture has been criticised as encouraging surface rather than deep learning as it may not necessarily stimulate thinking, may promote a view of learning as remembering masses of isolated detail and may encourage students to perceive the lecturer as an unapproachably remote authority concerned with getting information into students' memories. The task that the lecturer is facing, is paradoxically how to make 'lecturing' less like a lecture (passive, rigid, routine knowledge transmission) and more like an active communication between teacher and students.

Any technological teaching aid being used should be carefully integrated into the lecture and its purpose explained to students so that it is perceived to be relevant to the teaching and learning process and not merely a distraction. Lecturers who blindly adopt technology in their teaching will be open to a criticism that they are just using 'gimmicks' which add nothing to their teaching and are purely for entertainment. As McCarthy and Hatcher(2002) have said, "*The dangers for us in all of this, is to allow these potentially helpful tools, the technologies available to us, to divert us from what we are trying to achieve - good communication. We must not allow the technology to drive our communication. It will undoubtedly support and probably even influence and shape some aspects of our communication. But an awareness of just how seductive these new technologies are should act as a brake to keep control of how we use them.*"

There are certain elements unique to lecture presentation appeared to increase interest on the part of students. These elements include the use of colour, the line-by-line or concept-by-concept presentation of information, a well thought-out pre-organization, flexibility for adding graphics, and easy variation of size and type of fonts (Harknett & Cobane, 1997; Holzl, 1997). Aly *et al.* (2004) found that this type of lecture focused attention and reduced distraction, benefiting student learning. According to Szabo and Hastings (2000), the five most appreciated components of the method were variation of fonts, the use of illustrations, a preference for light-coloured background, the use of colours, and the line-by-line projection of lecture concepts.

Winn (2003, p. 113), sees using PowerPoint in the classroom as a way to "temporarily publish embellished teaching notes." Other teachers see it as a way to better organize themselves to lecture more clearly to students while helping them write accurate notes (Reinhardt, 1999). There are, however, many disadvantages to using PowerPoint in this narrow sense. PowerPoint presentations are not always the most effective way of teaching the curriculum. Winn (2003, p. 115) quotes students who refer to their classes taught primarily through PowerPoint as "death by PowerPoint." Any method of teaching gets stale when used exclusively and PowerPoint is no exception. The fact that it uses computers and graphics to present material does not make it less subject to becoming another "boring" lecture delivery system. Students do not necessarily find bulleted slides more stimulating (Reinhardt, 1999).

Tufte (2003), in an article entitled "PowerPoint is Evil," says the slides may help speakers outline their speeches, but suggests there are many properties of PowerPoint that may actually reduce the understandability of the content. First, Tufte suggestst he widespread use of bulleted lists in PowerPoint slides may suppress creative and critical thinking about lecture content since students may led to think in the same order as the order in which major points are listed. He also points out that students may be forced to view bad typography and poor chart layout made by presenters who are poor designers. Further, he maintains that some presenters select poorly-designed templates that distract audiences from the content of lectures. Another problem according to him is that many presenters include too much text on each slide and include distracting animated, point-to-point transitions. He concludes that PowerPoint is more useful for guiding and supporting a presenter than for helping students to understand and retain lecture material.

Despite PowerPoint's popularity in education, there are several issues associated with this presentation tool and how it is used in the classroom. Many argue that PowerPoint has a 'tendency to produce a disembodied and decontextualized learning environment' for students (Pauw, 2002, p. 39) because: 'bullets leave critical relationships unspecified ... Thus, unless presenters fill in the gaps, people cannot see the whole picture or understand the important relationships' (Shaw *et al.* 1998, p. 45). Johnson (2005) argued that in the classroom, PowerPoint promotes student inactivity because slides are presented one after another, and

contain little, if any, data or information created by students. Students passively view slides displaying the results of knowledge construction rather than actively participating in their own knowledge construction.

According to Wet (2006), PowerPoint has following features which can make PowerPoint a potentially lethal tool for effective teaching:

1. PowerPoint is wizard-driven and conceptually easy to use. The danger is that teachers may simply dump quantities of information on a series of slides without thinking through what to present and how to present it.
 2. The bells and whistles (clipart, animation, transitions, and timing) could be so beguiling that teachers overuse these features and merely distract students with visual overload that has no connection to the information presented. According to Murphy (2004), elaborate, busy PowerPoint presentations result in lower achievement on test scores.
 3. Design and layout templates may inhibit teacher creativity and suggest using only bullet points. This abbreviated way of presenting content results in what Tufte (2003) calls "foreshortening of evidence and thought" (p. 4). Using the typical PowerPoint layout suggests to students that this hierarchical single path structure is the model for organizing every type of content. It also breaks up the narrative and the data into slides and small fragments. It leads to rapid sequencing of shallow information, rather than a deep interaction with rich material.
 4. Teachers may rely on the PowerPoint presentation to engage students with content. The PowerPoint presentation is a small part of the whole instructional package. A research study by 3M suggests that presenters with visual aids are 43% more effective than those without; but how the presenter looks and speaks accounts for the majority of the audience's opinion of the presentation (Farwell, 2005).
- Effectively created PowerPoint slides will improve teaching and foster better interaction in the class, creating more in-depth learning. When creating presentations, teachers need to be sure to create effective slides that are relevant, interesting, and encourage class discussion. Merely placing lecture notes on text-

heavy slides with pretty graphics will not create a more lively and engaged class. Winn (2003) asserts that slides should use thought-provoking images that emphasize the main points of the lecture, not bulleted lists. He states "*imagery forces you to synthesize the textual component of your presentation*" (Winn, 2003, p. 115). Choosing photographs, clip art, simulations, or video-clips as the main component of the presentation will actively involve students in considering the topics of the lecture and engaging them in worthwhile interaction with the teacher and each other. Even less-than-perfect images on a slide will be more effective than text, evoking a response from students (Winn, 2003). The Internet is filled with searchable images that can be downloaded and placed in a presentation to jump-start those discussions.

Although PowerPoint presentations can be an effective teaching tool, teachers should consider more seriously how they use that tool to engage students with the curriculum. Teachers need to use a variety of teaching methods to keep students interested in learning. PowerPoint is only one of those tools. When using it, teachers should consider putting aside the text-heavy slides and using more imagery to make students critically think about the topic of the lesson.

The main benefit of PowerPoint presentations is engaging students not just through words, but also through visuals. Some students learn better by hearing, but other students learn better by seeing. Engaging students through the visual means provides some excitement that breaks down the daily routine of lectures. Vik (2004) identified the most common bad habits of PowerPoint users which distract considerably from the quality of their presentations.

1. Too much text on a slide

It is often impossible to read the text, due to the font size. Also, the audience is placed in a position of cognitive overload because they must simultaneously read text and listen to the presenter (Cooper, 2009).

2. Inappropriate background

Templates can be a tempting option, but users must be vigilant. Some are much too colourful or, in some cases, totally inappropriate for the content of the presentation (style that is too fun or too serious).

3. Too much animation or too many useless effects

Some animation can be quite useful in highlighting important ideas or messages, but again, you must be careful. Animation or sound effects that have no strategic purpose become a distraction that can decrease comprehension.

4. Too many slides

Too many slides for the length of the presentation force the presenter into a rhythm that the audience may have difficulty following (too much information coming from the presenter and from the audio-visual aids, all in too little time).

5. Graphics that are too complex

A graphic which contains too many statistics or a juxtaposition of statistics fails to transmit information effectively.

6. Lack of structure

Developing a coherent structure is the most important element of a good PowerPoint presentation. One must devote time to preparing one's message (its relevance, its coherence, its importance, etc.) and especially to reflecting on the most appropriate ways to communicate it (pictures, words, diagrams, etc.).

Lastly, it is important to remember that PowerPoint is just a tool. What is most important about a presentation is the message, not the medium.

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